

Promoting Online Learning Communities:
A systematic review on the instructional strategies and tools

AECT Proposal – Division of Distance Education

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Introduction

Online Learning Communities (OLC) has recently received increasing attention in the field of online education (Ke&Hoadley, 2009). Learning community helps promote positive learning experiences and better learning outcomes in distance learning environments (Stepich& Ertmer, 2003). However, one inevitable tradeoffs in an online learning environment is a decrease in the quality of social interaction and the degree of social presence. Social interaction is innate in traditional face-to-face classrooms. Among the essential components of a community, interaction between the members is deemed to be the one crucial factor that makes a community alive. It is not only a critical element in helping the learners to develop a sense of belongingness within a learning community, but also determines the dynamics of the learning community. Another crucial element is social presence. Social presence is defined as “the degree of awareness of another person in an interaction and the consequent appreciation of an interpersonal relationship” (Tu, 2002, p. 294). As the degree of social presence declines, the communication is perceived as more impersonal. According to Argyle and Dean (1965) and Wiener and Mehrabian(1968), the two components of social presence are intimacy and immediacy. Intimacy refers to physical proximity, visual cues (such as eye contact, body language) and topic of communication (during the information exchange). Immediacy regards the psychological distance that is set by the signaler to the receiver in an event of communication.

There has been a call for an effort to create a “human touch of attentiveness to their students” in distance learning (Regalbuto et al., 1999, p.2), and facilitate online learning experiences that more closely resemble traditionally accepted practices (Meyen, Tangen, &Lian, 1999)in response to this issue. The low social presence in online learning environments creates an invisible obstacle that undermines quality social interactions, and thus hinders online learners’ development of a sense of a learning community.

Methods

A systematic literature review was conducted to examine the current practice and formats in helping students form learning communities in online environments by promoting social interaction and social presence. Combinations of keywords (online, learning community, virtual learning community, learning community building, social interaction, social presence) were used in searching the literature from 1990-2012 in ERIC, PsychInfo, Academic Search Premier, E-Journals. The criteria for inclusion of articles were (1) online or hybrid instruction, (2) promoting

OLC, (3) promoting social interaction or presence. After screening the initial literature search results using the inclusion criteria, 61 articles were identified and included in the review. The researchers reviewed the articles based on a conceptual framework that consists of four components: theoretical conception, interaction, social presence, and tools.

Results & Discussion

The preliminary findings from the review of the selected articles can be divided into four categories as described as follows.

Factors affecting OLC. There are some factors that could affect a formation of an OLC in different ways. First of all, helping students develop a sense of OLC is the first step to establish toward forming a functional and strong OLC. The variable of sense of OLC could be affected by a number of variables. These variables could be personal (behaviors, personal assumed roles), social, or interpersonal (trust, team commitment, task conflict, relationship conflict). Additionally, research has also found that an OLC is not formed instantaneously. Rather, it is a process of different stages with different levels of interactions among the community members.

Explicit instructional strategies for promoting OLC building. It was also found that a number of instructional strategies or design have been used in helping students to form OLC in their courses. The instructional strategies or design reported in the literature were either explicit or implicit in terms of making the students aware of the building of their OLC. Eksisozluk, a Turkish online collaborative learning community was one example of explicit design that used this approach in achieving the goal of promoting OLC. This online collaborative community used features such as sharing a common goal (members were required to be Ph.D. degree seekers), community history, and individual identities were provided to help increase the sense of OLC among the community members.

Implicit instructional design/support for promoting OLC building. The majority of the instructional designs for helping OLC building fall into the category of implicit approach. These designs mainly targeted two critical elements in the construction and maintenance of OLC, which were interaction and social presence. Examples of implicit OLC building design for promoting interaction among OLC members include community of inquiry, audio-based asynchronous learning forum, action learning online method, online discussion, collaborative learning, collaborative problem-based learning, social tasks, social learning techniques, peer assisted learning community, and student-led spontaneous online discussion facilitation. Another set of instructional designs were aimed at enhancing the social presence. These designs included providing more means for access or navigating (social navigation) to other community members, teaching presence, or online mentors. The effects of these implicit instructional designs for OLC building were mixed. When comparing the two categories of designs, the results showed that explicit OLC designs seemed to be more effective than implicit designs. Then the question is: Is making the purpose of the design explicit necessary for the effects of the design to take place? Are there any negative effects by making the students aware of the purpose of the instructional design? Further research will be needed to answer these questions.

Tools/technology. Besides the traditional threaded online discussion, a number of tools or technologies were reported being used in facilitating the building of OLC. Among which, blogs, wikis, podcasts, audio-based forum, as well as photovoice were some of the examples.

Conclusion

Learning community is a vital component in fostering rich learning experience. It provides students not only with intellectual support from peers and the instructors, but also social, psychological, and sometimes emotional support. Building learning community in online environments presents challenges due to the limited social presence and interactions. More research effort is needed in elucidating the effectiveness of explicit and implicit instructional design on promoting OLC, as well as the types of supporting technology.

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Note: The references for the articles being reviewed will be available upon request.